

Direct measurements of V_{tb} and constraints on the Wtb anomalous couplings

N. Brusino, on behalf of the ATLAS and CMS Collaborations.

*Department of Physics & Astronomy, University of Pittsburgh, 4200 Fifth Avenue
Pittsburgh, PA USA 15260*

nello.bruscino@cern.ch

The latest results from ATLAS and CMS about V_{tb} and the Wtb vertex are presented. Single top quark production cross sections allows to directly constrain the V_L coupling while W -boson helicity, asymmetry and the 3-angle analyses provide constraints on the anomalous coupling with different levels of generality. A global fit which combines all the mentioned analyses, except the 3-angle one, from Tevatron and the Large Hadron Collider, leads to significant sensitivity improvements, especially when compared with the current expectation for the High Luminosity run at the LHC.

Keywords: top physics; single top; V_{tb} ; Wtb vertex; CKM matrix; CERN; ATLAS; CMS.

1. Introduction

At hadron colliders, top quarks are predominantly produced in pairs ($t\bar{t}$) via the flavour-conserving strong interaction, but single top-quark production can occur via charged-current electroweak processes involving a Wtb vertex. At leading order in QCD perturbation theory, three sub-processes contribute to single top-quark production: an exchange of a virtual W boson either in the t-channel or in the s-channel, or the associated production of a top quark with an on-shell W boson (Wt).

Within the Standard Model the top quark decays through the electroweak interaction into an on-shell W boson and a b -quark, with a lifetime much shorter than the time scale necessary to depolarise the spin. The information on the top-quark spin can thus be obtained from its decay products. The produced real W boson also possesses a polarisation (or helicity state), which can be extracted from angular distributions of its decay products through the measurement of spin-dependent observables. Furthermore, as a consequence of the vector minus axial-vector (V-A) form of the Wtb vertex in the Standard Model, the produced top quarks in the single-top t-channel are highly polarised, in particular along the direction of the spectator-quark momentum.

Measuring the top-quark polarisation and the W -boson spin observables provides a powerful probe for studying the Wtb vertex in both top-quark production

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and decay. New physics effects resulting in corrections to the Wtb vertex would affect the top-quark and W -boson polarisations. In the effective operator formalism the most general Wtb Lagrangian can be written as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{Wtb} = -\frac{g}{\sqrt{2}}\bar{b}\gamma^\mu(V_L P_L + V_R P_R)tW_\mu^- - \frac{g}{\sqrt{2}}\bar{b}\frac{i\sigma^{\mu\nu}q_\nu}{m_W}(g_L P_L + g_R P_R)tW_\mu^- + \text{H.c.}$$

The constants $V_{L,R}$ and $g_{L,R}$ are the left- and right-handed vector and tensor couplings, respectively. In the Standard Model at tree level the coupling V_L is the V_{tb} element of the quark-mixing Cabibbo-Kobayashi-Maskawa (CKM) matrix that is close to one, while the anomalous couplings V_R and $g_{L,R}$ are all zero. Deviations from these values would provide hints of physics beyond the Standard Model, and complex values would imply that the top-quark decay has a CP-violating component.

There are multiple ways we can probe the Wtb vertex structure: the following sections will summarise the most recent results by the ATLAS and CMS collaborations, going from measurements with the most stringent assumptions (in the real and imaginary part of the coupling terms) to the most general ones.

2. Direct constraints on V_L

The left handed term $V_L = f_{LV}V_{tb}$ can be inferred from cross section measurements, where non-SM couplings are neglected; f_{LV} being a model-independent left-handed real form factor, encapsulating non-SM contributions. Figure 1 shows the most recent results by ATLAS and CMS. The most precise result is the Run 1 combination by CMS¹, with $V_L = 0.998 \pm 0.041$. A Run1 combination of the ATLAS and CMS measurements is currently ongoing.

3. W -helicity fractions

The W -boson polarisation fractions $F_{0,L,R}$ are sensitive to variations of anomalous couplings and are measured in $t\bar{t}$ events: four real couplings are considered in this case. Events are reconstructed with either one muon or one electron, along with four jets in the final state, with two of the jets being identified as originating from b -quarks. Then a kinematic likelihood fitter is utilised to reconstruct and identify all $t\bar{t}$ decay products. The helicity angle θ^* is defined as the angle between the direction of either the down-type quark or the charged lepton arising from the W boson decay and the reversed direction of the top quark, both in the rest frame of the W boson.

In the CMS analysis at 8 TeV², top events $N_{t\bar{t}}$ are reweighted, according to top decay function, by the weight

$$w(\cos\theta_{\text{gen}}^*; \vec{F}) = \left[\frac{3}{8}F_L(1 - \cos\theta_{\text{gen}}^*)^2 + \frac{3}{4}F_0 \sin^2\theta_{\text{gen}}^* + \frac{3}{8}F_R(1 + \cos\theta_{\text{gen}}^*)^2 \right] / \left[\frac{3}{8}F_L^{\text{SM}}(1 - \cos\theta_{\text{gen}}^*)^2 + \frac{3}{4}F_0^{\text{SM}} \sin^2\theta_{\text{gen}}^* + \frac{3}{8}F_R^{\text{SM}}(1 + \cos\theta_{\text{gen}}^*)^2 \right]$$

Fig. 1. Summary of the ATLAS and CMS extractions of the CKM matrix element V_{tb} from single top quark measurements. For each result, the contribution to the total uncertainty originating from the uncertainty on the theoretical prediction for the single top production cross-section is shown along with the uncertainty originating from the experimental measurement of the cross-section.

and this parameterisation is employed in maximisation of likelihood function $\mathcal{L}(\vec{F})$. Results are in agreement with the SM prediction at 95 %C.L., as shown in Figure 2.

The ATLAS approach at 8 TeV³ consists, instead, in reweighing the final reconstructed $\cos\theta^*$ distribution to produce templates for F_0 , F_L and F_R (per-lepton channel) and use them in a combined likelihood fit. Results are in agreement with SM predictions and are also reinterpreted in terms of anomalous couplings, as shown in Figures 3, assuming $V_L = 1$ and V_R or $g_L = 0$.

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Fig. 2. Left: the measured W boson helicity fractions in the (F_0, F_L) plane. The dashed and solid ellipses enclose the allowed two-dimensional 68% and 95% C.L. regions, for the combined $\ell + \text{jets}$ measurement, taking into account the correlations on the total (including systematic) uncertainties. The error bars give the one-dimensional 68% C.L. interval for the separate F_0 and F_L measurements, with the inner-tick (outer-tick) mark representing the statistical (total) uncertainty. Right: the corresponding allowed regions for the real components of the anomalous couplings g_L and g_R at 68% and 95% C.L., for $V_L = 1$ and $V_R = 0$. A region near $\text{Re}(g_L) = 0$ and $\text{Re}(g_R) \gg 0$, allowed by the fit but excluded by the CMS single top quark production measurement, is omitted. The SM predictions are shown as stars.

Fig. 3. (a) Limits on the anomalous left- and right-handed tensor couplings of the Wtb decay vertex as obtained from the measured W boson helicity fractions from the leptonic analyser. (b) Limits on the right-handed vector and tensor coupling. As the couplings are assumed to be real, the real part corresponds to the magnitude. Unconsidered couplings are fixed to their SM values.

4. Wtb couplings in the single-top t -channel

Single top-quark production and decay observables (angular distributions, asymmetries in specific polarisation bases) significantly reduces the allowed regions for anomalous coupling (especially the imaginary components). The CMS analysis at 7 and 8 TeV⁴ is performed using events with one muon and two or three jets. A Bayesian neural network technique is used to distinguish possible right-handed vector or left-/right-handed tensor structures from the SM left-handed vector structure in the t -channel single top quark events. Different scenarios are considered: results are observed to be consistent with the SM prediction. The combined observed and

expected two-dimensional contours in the (f_V^L, f_V^R) , (f_V^L, f_T^L) and (f_V^L, f_T^R) spaces are shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Combined $\sqrt{s} = 7$ and 8 TeV observed and expected exclusion limits in the two-dimensional planes $(f_V^L, |f_V^R|)$ (top-left), $(f_V^L, |f_T^L|)$ (top-right), and (f_V^L, f_T^R) (bottom) at 68% and 95% C.L..

5. Global constraints

A global fit approach⁵ to the Wtb vertex structure combines recently proposed forward-backward asymmetries with helicity fractions and single top cross section measurements for the first time, in a very general model, where the real and imaginary components of all couplings are allowed to vary simultaneously. The limits on anomalous contributions to the Wtb vertex are calculated using the latest and most precise top quark measurements at the LHC and Tevatron. The 95% C.L. limits on the anomalous couplings allowed regions are obtained with the TOPFIT program⁶ and shown in Figure 5, where V_L is set to 1. The TOPFIT program fits the Wtb vertex parameterised by the general EFT Lagrangian.

6. The 3-angle analysis

The triple-differential angular decay rates provides the most general results, without any assumption on the different anomalous couplings. Five generalised helicity fractions (three independent: f_1, f_1^+, f_0^+) and phases (δ_+, δ_-), as well as the polarisation of the produced top quark are determined simultaneously, including all correlations. The analysis at 8 TeV⁷ is carried out in a Fourier-dual space of coefficients in an angular expansion. This leads to the following expression for the

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Fig. 5. Three-dimensional representation of the 95% C.L. limits on the allowed regions for $\text{Re}(g_R)$, $\text{Im}(g_R)$, $\text{Re}(V_R)$ (left) and the corresponding two-dimensional regions of $\text{Im}(g_R)$ as a function of $\text{Re}(g_R)$ (right).

triple-differential decay rate for polarised top quarks in terms of the three angles (θ , θ^* , and ϕ^*) and the top-quark polarisation P ,

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(\theta, \theta^*, \phi^*; P) &= \frac{1}{N} \frac{d^3 N}{d(\cos \theta) d\Omega^*} = \frac{1}{8\pi} \left\{ \frac{3}{4} |A_{1, \frac{1}{2}}|^2 (1 + P \cos \theta)(1 + \cos \theta^*)^2 \right. \\ &\quad + \frac{3}{4} |A_{-1, -\frac{1}{2}}|^2 (1 - P \cos \theta)(1 - \cos \theta^*)^2 \\ &\quad + \frac{3}{2} \left(|A_{0, \frac{1}{2}}|^2 (1 - P \cos \theta) + |A_{0, -\frac{1}{2}}|^2 (1 + P \cos \theta) \right) \sin^2 \theta^* \\ &\quad - \frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2} P \sin \theta \sin \theta^* (1 + \cos \theta^*) \text{Re} \left[e^{i\phi^*} A_{1, \frac{1}{2}} A_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^* \right] \\ &\quad \left. - \frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2} P \sin \theta \sin \theta^* (1 - \cos \theta^*) \text{Re} \left[e^{-i\phi^*} A_{-1, -\frac{1}{2}} A_{0, -\frac{1}{2}}^* \right] \right\} = \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^1 \sum_{l=0}^2 \sum_{m=-k}^k a_{k,l,m} M_{k,l}^m(\theta, \theta^*, \phi^*), \end{aligned}$$

where A_{λ_W, λ_b} are the four helicity amplitudes, λ_W and λ_b being the helicities of the W boson and the b -quark, respectively; while the $a_{k,l,m}$ represent the angular coefficients to be determined and $M_{k,l}^m(\theta, \theta^*, \phi^*)$ are orthonormal functions over the three angles. This method permits an analytic deconvolution of detector effects including both resolution and efficiency, while permitting a simultaneous determination of the real and imaginary parts of all of the anomalous couplings at the Wtb vertex, in addition to the polarisation of the top quark produced in the t -channel. The fit results are shown in Figure 6: None of the measurements make assumptions about the value of any of the other parameters or couplings and all of them are in agreement with the Standard Model.

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Fig. 6. The likelihood contours of (a) $|g_L/V_L|$ as a function of $|V_R/V_L|$ and (b) $Im|g_R/V_L|$ as a function of $Re|g_R/V_L|$ are shown. The red point, which overlaps with the origin of the x - and y -axis, represents the SM expectation while a black x mark indicates the observed value. The 68% and 95% C.L. regions are shown in green and yellow, respectively.

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